

Evolutionary dynamics and the evolution of multiplayer cooperation in a subdivided population

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Abstract

The classical models of evolution have been developed to incorporate structured populations using evolutionary graph theory and, more recently, a new framework has been developed to allow for more flexible population structures which potentially change through time and can accommodate multiplayer games with variable group sizes. In this paper we extend this work in three key ways. Firstly by developing a complete set of evolutionary dynamics so that the range of dynamic processes used in classical evolutionary graph theory can be applied. Secondly, by building upon previous models to allow for a general subpopulation structure, where all subpopulation members have a common movement distribution. Subpopulations can have varying levels of stability, represented by the proportion of interactions occurring between subpopulation members; in our representation of the population all subpopulation members are represented by a single vertex. In conjunction with this we extend the important concept of temperature (the temperature of a vertex is the sum of all the weights coming into that vertex; generally, the higher the temperature, the higher the rate of turnover of individuals at a vertex). Finally, we have used these new developments to consider the evolution of cooperation in a class of populations which possess this subpopulation structure using a multiplayer public goods game. We show that cooperation can evolve providing that subpopulations are sufficiently stable, with the smaller the subpopulations the easier it is for cooperation to evolve. We introduce a new concept of temperature, namely “subgroup temperature”, which can be used to explain our results.

1. Introduction

2 Evolutionary game theory has proved to be a very successful way of mod-
3 elling the evolution of, and behaviour within, populations. The classical models

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4 mainly focused on well-mixed populations playing two player games [31, 30], or
5 alternatively playing games against the entire population [30]. Simple models
6 such as the Hawk-Dove game [29] and the sex ratio game [20] have been used
7 to explain important biological phenomena.

8 These models were developed to consider finite populations explicitly [34,
9 Chapters 6-9] (although see [32, 33] for important earlier non-game theoretic
10 work) and structured populations using the now widespread methodology of
11 evolutionary graph theory originated in [26] (see also [3, 9, 52, 27], and [1, 44]
12 for reviews). Such population structures can have a profound effect on the result
13 of the evolutionary process even when individuals have a fixed fitness [26, 28, 40].
14 Further, even for a given structure, the rules of the evolutionary dynamics have
15 a significant effect on the evolution of the population.

16 Previous work has investigated a number of important questions, the most
17 widely considered being how cooperation can evolve. The evolution of cooper-
18 ation, where individuals make sacrifices to help others, can seem paradoxical
19 within the context of natural selection, especially amongst unrelated individu-
20 als. There are a number of ways that mathematical modelling has demonstrated
21 that cooperation can occur [35]; one key way is through the presence of popula-
22 tion structure, which can mean that cooperative individuals are more likely to
23 interact with other cooperators, which makes them resistant to exploitation by
24 defectors [36, 42]. In particular, this is true for structures where individuals are
25 heterogeneous [43] allowing hubs or clusters of cooperators to form. The dynam-
26 ics that one uses are also important; for example [36] showed that death-birth or
27 birth-death dynamics with selection on the second event promotes cooperation
28 but not when selection happens in the first event.

29 One limitation of evolutionary graph theory is that it naturally lends itself
30 to pairwise games, whereas real populations can often involve the simultaneous
31 interaction of many individuals [45, 15]. Multiplayer games, whilst more com-
32 mon in economic modelling [21, 6], have become used in increasing frequency
33 within evolutionary games starting with [38, 7] (see also [14, 18]) and it is im-
34 portant to incorporate these too into the modelling of structured populations.
35 A multiplayer public goods game [4, 5, 19, 54], (and this type of game is central
36 to our paper too, see Section 2.2) has been used in evolutionary graph theory
37 [25, 51, 24, 41, 56], but this typically involves forming an individual and all of
38 its neighbours into a group and allowing them to play a game. Although this is
39 convenient, it is not really natural because there is no mechanism for deciding
40 how individuals spend their time, and so how they share that time with others,
41 either singly or in groups.

42 More recently a general framework has been developed [10, 13, 8, 11] which
43 considers the interaction of populations in a more flexible way, where groups of
44 any size can form, with different propensity potentially depending upon a num-
45 ber of factors, including the history of the process. Crucially, the key elements
46 of evolutionary graph theory of population structure, game and evolutionary
47 dynamics occur for this new framework too; this makes it capable of analysing
48 different spatial structures whilst providing the flexibility for different multi-
49 player interactions. Prior to the current paper, the actual applications of the

Figure 1: The fully independent model from [10]. There are N individuals who are distributed over M places such that I_n visits place P_m with probability p_{nm} . Individuals interact with one another when they meet, for example, I_1 and I_2 can interact with one another when they meet in P_1 .

50 above framework have been limited. In particular only a single evolutionary
 51 dynamics (the BDB dynamics from the current paper) has been used, and only
 52 relatively simple populations, which resembled those in evolutionary graph theory
 53 (the population consisting of individuals each resident at a unique graph
 54 vertex) have been considered.

55 In this paper we further develop the general theory of the framework origi-
 56 nated in [10]. We first show how to represent subpopulations using a reduced
 57 graphical representation within our structure, which will then allow us to po-
 58 tentially consider larger populations with a richer structure than previously. We
 59 then demonstrate how to apply a standard set of evolutionary dynamics to con-
 60 sider a range of evolutionary processes. This is vital since, as mentioned above,
 61 dynamics can have a big effect on the outcome of evolution within other models,
 62 including evolutionary graph theory, and as we will see, this is certainly also
 63 true for our work. Finally we use these new tools to consider the evolution of
 64 cooperation using a multiplayer public goods game [51, 48, 49, 4] and show that
 65 cooperation can occur when both the structure and evolutionary dynamics act
 66 together in favour of the cooperators.

67 The paper is structured as follows: in Section 2 the model framework is
 68 described, including how to incorporate subpopulations. In Section 3 a standard
 69 set of evolutionary dynamics to be used with our model are defined. In Section
 70 4 we introduce and discuss the important concepts of fixation probability and
 71 temperature. In Section 5 we study the evolution of cooperation in our model
 72 with subpopulations. Section 6 is then a general discussion.

73 2. A framework for modelling evolution in structured populations

74 A framework for modelling the movement of individuals was presented in
 75 [10]. This is a very general and flexible methodology, the details of which are not
 76 necessary for the current paper. Below we describe the fully independent version
 77 of this framework in which individuals move independently of each other and

Table of Notation

<i>Notation</i>	<i>Definition</i>	<i>Description</i>
N	$\in \mathbb{Z}^+ \setminus \{0\}$	Population size.
M	$\in \mathbb{Z}^+ \setminus \{0\}$	Number of places.
I_n		Individual n .
P_m		Place m .
\mathcal{G}	$\subset \{1, 2, \dots, N\}$	Group of individuals.
p_{nm}	$\in [0, 1]$	Probability that I_n is in P_m .
$\chi(m, \mathcal{G})$	$\in [0, 1]$	Probability of group \mathcal{G} forming in place P_m .
F_n	$\in (0, \infty)$	Fitness of individual I_n .
$R_{n,m,\mathcal{G}}$	$\in [0, \infty)$	Payoff to I_n in \mathcal{G} present in P_m .
h	$\in (0, \infty)$	Home fidelity.
d	$\in \mathbb{Z}^+ \setminus \{0\}$	Number of neighbours.
r, v	$\in (0, \infty)$	Background fitness, reward.
C, D		Cooperator, Defector.
$R_{c,d}^C$	$\in [0, \infty)$	Payoff to cooperator in a group (including itself) of c cooperators and d defectors.
$R_{n,G}$	$\in [0, \infty)$	Payoff to I_n in group G .
\mathcal{S}	$= \{n : I_n \text{ is cooperator}\}$	State of the population.
\mathcal{N}	$= \{1, 2, \dots, N\}$	State in which all individuals are cooperators.
$P_{\mathcal{S}\mathcal{S}'}$	$\in [0, 1]$	State transition probability.
$\rho_{\mathcal{S}}^C$	$\in [0, 1]$	Probability of fixating in \mathcal{N} when initial state is \mathcal{S} .
ρ^C	$\in [0, 1]$	Mean fixation probability of a cooperator.
$\mathbf{W} = (w_{ij})$	$w_{ij} \in (0, \infty)$	Weighted adjacency matrix that represents an evolutionary graph.
v_n		Vertex n of an evolutionary graph.
b_i	$\in [0, 1]$	Probability I_i is selected for birth.
d_{ij}	$\in [0, 1]$	Probability I_i replaces I_j given I_i is selected for birth.
d_i	$\in [0, 1]$	Probability I_i is selected for death.
b_{ij}	$\in [0, 1]$	Probability I_i replaces I_j given I_j is selected for death.
\mathbf{r}_{ij}	$\in [0, 1]$	Probability I_i replaces I_j .
T_i^+	$= \sum_j w_{ij}$	Out temperature of I_i .
T_i^-	$= \sum_j w_{ji}$	In temperature of I_j .
\mathcal{Q}_m	$\subset \{1, 2, \dots, N\}$	Subpopulation of individuals.
$T_{\mathcal{Q}_m}$	$= \sum_{i \in \mathcal{N} \setminus \mathcal{Q}_m} \sum_{j \in \mathcal{Q}_m} w_{ij}$	Strict subpopulation temperature.

Table 1: Notation used in the paper.

78 independently of the population's history (any past movements), and a version
79 of the fully independent model called the territorial raider model as introduced
80 in [10] and further developed in [8]. We then develop a generalization of this
81 model, which then forms the basis of much of the work in this paper, although

82 we note that Section 3 in particular is more general. Important terms used in
 83 the current paper are given in Table 1.

84 *2.1. The population structure*

85 We begin by introducing the fully independent model. Consider a population
 86 made up of N individuals I_1, \dots, I_N who can move around M places P_1, \dots, P_M .
 87 The probability of individual I_n being at place P_m is denoted by p_{nm} ; see Figure
 88 1 for a visual representation using a bi-partite graph. When individuals move
 89 around they form groups. Let \mathcal{G} denote any group of individuals, then the
 90 probability $\chi(m, \mathcal{G})$ that group \mathcal{G} forms in place P_m is given by

$$91 \quad \chi(m, \mathcal{G}) = \prod_{i \in \mathcal{G}} p_{im} \prod_{j \notin \mathcal{G}} (1 - p_{jm}). \quad (2.1)$$

93 We can show from equation (2.1) that

$$94 \quad 1 = \sum_m \sum_{\substack{\mathcal{G} \\ n \in \mathcal{G}}} \chi(m, \mathcal{G}) \quad \forall n. \quad (2.2)$$

96 This follows intuitively from the fact that individual I_n has to be present in some
 97 place P_m in some group \mathcal{G} at any given time. The mean size of an individual's
 98 group (see also [13]) is given by

$$99 \quad \bar{G} = \sum_m \sum_{\mathcal{G}} \frac{\chi(m, \mathcal{G}) |\mathcal{G}|^2}{\sum_m \sum_{\mathcal{G}} \chi(m, \mathcal{G}) |\mathcal{G}|} = \sum_m \sum_{\mathcal{G}} \frac{\chi(m, \mathcal{G}) |\mathcal{G}|^2}{N} \quad (2.3)$$

101 where the simplification of the denominator follows from equation (2.2).

102 When a group of individuals is formed they will then interact with one
 103 another. In particular, individual I_n will receive a payoff that depends upon
 104 the group \mathcal{G} it is present in and the place P_m occupied by this group. This
 105 is denoted as $R_{n,m,\mathcal{G}}$ and was referred to in [10] as a *direct group interaction*
 106 *payoff* because individual I_n only interacts with other individuals with whom
 107 it is directly present ([10] allowed for a more general class of payoff but this
 108 is the only type we will consider, and hence will just refer to it as the payoff).
 109 Individual I_n 's fitness is then calculated by averaging its payoffs over all possible
 110 groups and places that these groups can form as follows:

$$111 \quad F_n = \sum_m \sum_{\substack{\mathcal{G} \\ n \in \mathcal{G}}} \chi(m, \mathcal{G}) R_{n,m,\mathcal{G}}. \quad (2.4)$$

112 We now move on to consider the territorial raider model. In the territorial
 113 raider model, each individual I_n has its own place P_n with no unoccupied places
 114 and, therefore, there is a one-to-one correspondence between individuals and
 115 places. A graph is used to represent the structure of the population where
 116 each vertex represents an individual and its corresponding home such that two
 117 connected individuals can raid each other's home places (see Figure 2). The

Figure 2: The territorial raider model of [10, 8]. (a) Population structure represented using a graph where vertices represent individuals and places. Individual I_n lives in place P_n and can visit any neighbouring places. For example, the home place of I_1 is place P_1 but it can visit places P_2, P_3 and P_4 . (b) An alternative visualization on a bi-partite graph where individuals and places are clearly separated.

118 probability of raiding another's home place is governed by a common movement
 119 parameter called home fidelity, h , that measures an individuals' preference for
 120 their home place. In particular, an individual with d neighbours would stay on
 121 their home place with probability $h/(h + d)$ or raid any one of its neighbours'
 122 home places with an equal probability of $1/(h + d)$ (see Figure 2).

Figure 3: The generalized territorial raider model. (a) Individuals that are members of subpopulation Q_m live in place P_m but can visit neighbouring places. The territory of subpopulation $\{I_1, I_2\}$ consists of places P_1 and P_2 , the territory of subpopulation $\{I_3, I_4\}$ consists of places P_1, P_2 and P_3 , the territory of subpopulation $\{I_5\}$ consists of P_2 and P_3 . (b) An alternative visualization as multiplayer interactions on a bi-partite graph where individuals and places are clearly separated.

123 We now generalise the territorial raider model to include subpopulations,
 124 based upon their movement distributions. We will see that individuals within a
 125 given subpopulation are more likely to interact with each other than with mem-
 126 bers of other subpopulations, and this will affect the success of their strategies.

127 Consider the fully independent model. We define a subpopulation of individ-
 128 uals as a division of individuals from the main population that is *well-mixed* [10],
 129 which simply means that all of these individuals have an identical distribution
 130 over the places. In particular, for a subpopulation Q we have that $p_{im} = p_{jm}$
 131 $\forall i, j \in Q$ and $m = 1, \dots, M$. This can be visualised in terms of a bipartite
 132 graph as in Figure 1 where the vertices are now occupied by subpopulations

133 rather than individuals. This subpopulation structure is thus a special case of
 134 the fully independent model.

135 For simplicity we will assume that individuals move as they do in the terri-
 136 torial raider model; thus our model is a generalization of the territorial raider
 137 model. A population of N individuals is divided into M non-overlapping sub-
 138 populations $\mathcal{Q}_1, \dots, \mathcal{Q}_M$ where $|\mathcal{Q}_m| \geq 0$ such that $N = \sum_m |\mathcal{Q}_m|$. We will
 139 assume that individuals in subpopulation \mathcal{Q}_m treat place P_m as their home
 140 place, so that there is a one-to-one correspondence between subpopulations and
 141 places. However, because we allow subpopulations to be empty, we can have
 142 places in which no individuals reside. As before, the movement probabilities of
 143 the individuals is governed by the home fidelity h . In particular, a subpopula-
 144 tion \mathcal{Q}_m that can visit d neighbouring places will stay in home place P_m with
 145 probability $h/(h+d)$ or move to one of its neighbouring places with probability
 146 $1/(h+d)$. Note that when there is one individual in each subpopulation, that is
 147 $|\mathcal{Q}_m| = 1 \forall m$, we recover the original territorial raider model. This information
 148 can be visually represented in two different ways as shown in Figure 3, which
 149 includes a graph whose vertices represent both subpopulations and places. This
 150 generalized territorial raider model will be the basis of our detailed investigation
 151 of the evolution of cooperation in Section 5.

152 2.2. A multiplayer public goods game

153 A multiplayer Hawk-Dove game [46] and a public goods game were con-
 154 sidered in [8], though there are other games that can be considered like the
 155 multiplayer stag hunt game [37].

156 In this paper we focus only on the multiplayer public goods game based on
 157 the game defined by [51], where an individual's payoff is an average of two player
 158 public goods games (just a version of the standard prisoner's dilemma) played
 159 with each of its group mates. Players can either cooperate (C) or defect (D).
 160 A cooperator always pays a cost 1 so that the other player receives a reward
 161 v and a defector pays no cost but only receives a reward when present with a
 162 cooperator. Note that the cost is set to 1 because scaling all the payoffs by
 163 some other cost value does not affect the outcome of the game and, therefore,
 164 the reward v is a multiple of the cost. The payoff matrix is thus given by

$$165 \begin{array}{c|cc} & C & D \\ \hline C & v-1 & -1 \\ D & v & 0 \end{array} . \quad (2.5)$$

166

167 In [51] and most models involving public goods games, individuals are never
 168 alone, and so what happens in the case they are alone is not considered. How-
 169 ever, in our case it is possible for an individual to be alone, for example, an
 170 individual could remain on its home place and not be raided. As in [8], we will
 171 assume that a lone cooperator still pays a cost but does not receive a reward
 172 and lone defectors receive nothing. There are other ways that we can allocate
 173 rewards to lone individuals; for example, in [22] there is a specific strategy, the
 174 loner strategy, where cooperators choose to be alone and not pay a cost. Our

Dynamics

BDB	$b_i = \frac{F_i}{\sum_n F_n}, d_{ij} = \frac{w_{ij}}{\sum_n w_{in}}$	BDD	$b_i = \frac{1}{N}, d_{ij} = \frac{w_{ij}F_j^{-1}}{\sum_n w_{in}F_n^{-1}}$
DBD	$d_j = \frac{F_j^{-1}}{\sum_n F_n^{-1}}, b_{ij} = \frac{w_{ij}}{\sum_n w_{nj}}$	DBB	$d_j = \frac{1}{N}, b_{ij} = \frac{w_{ij}F_i}{\sum_n w_{nj}F_n}$
LB	$\tau_{ij} = \frac{w_{ij}F_i}{\sum_{n,k} w_{nk}F_n}$	LD	$\tau_{ij} = \frac{w_{ij}F_j^{-1}}{\sum_{n,k} w_{nk}F_k^{-1}}$

Table 2: Dynamics defined using the replacement weight as in [40]. In each case, B (D) is appended to the name of the dynamics if selection happens in the birth (death) event.

175 choice seems a natural generalisation of the prisoners dilemma model [51], where
 176 individuals pay a cost but do not benefit from their own contributions. We note
 177 that our version makes cooperation harder to evolve than the alternatives. Thus
 178 if cooperators thrive in a population using our model, this can be thought of as
 179 strong support for the evolution of cooperation.

180 In the multiplayer public goods game, the payoffs to cooperators and defec-
 181 tors playing within a group of c cooperators and d defectors (including them-
 182 selves) is then respectively given by

$$183 \quad R_{c,d}^C = \begin{cases} r - 1, & c = 1 \\ r - 1 + \frac{c-1}{c+d-1}v, & c > 1 \end{cases} \quad \text{and} \quad R_{c,d}^D = \begin{cases} r, & c = 0 \\ r + \frac{c}{c+d-1}v, & c > 0 \end{cases} \quad (2.6)$$

185 where r is a background payoff, which is also a multiple of the cost, that every
 186 individual receives, representing the contribution from activities that are not
 187 related to the games. Generally, the effect of selection is weaker the larger
 188 the value of r (for example, see [12], Chapter 2). The payoff is then given by
 189 $R_{n,m,\mathcal{G}} \equiv R_{c,d}^C$ ($\equiv R_{c,d}^D$) when I_n is a cooperator (defector) and $|\mathcal{G}| = c+d$, which
 190 can then be substituted into Equation 2.4 to find the individual's fitness. Note
 191 that here the payoffs do not depend upon the place occupied by the individuals,
 192 that is, $R_{n,m,\mathcal{G}} \equiv R_{n,\mathcal{G}}$.

193 3. Evolutionary dynamics

194 In this section we revisit the standard dynamics of evolutionary graph theory,
 195 before demonstrating how we can adapt each of them to our framework. For
 196 the current work there will actually only be two distinct dynamics, but for more
 197 general cases each will be distinct, and so it is important to consider them all.
 198 We start by recalling the dynamics from evolutionary graph theory.

199 3.1. Evolutionary dynamics in evolutionary graph theory

200 An evolutionary graph [26, 40] is a graph represented by a weighted adja-
 201 cency matrix $\mathbf{W} = (w_{ij})$ where $w_{ij} \in [0, \infty)$ is referred to as the replacement

202 weight. Each vertex v_n of the evolutionary graph is occupied by one individual
 203 and if $w_{ij} > 0$ then the individual on v_i can place a copy of itself in v_j by
 204 replacing the individual there. It is assumed that the weights are chosen so that
 205 the evolutionary graph is strongly connected, which means that there is a route
 206 of finite length between any pair of vertices v_i and v_j . The weighted adjacency
 207 matrix \mathbf{W} is therefore said to define the replacement structure.

208 Assuming that there is only one replacement per update event, there are
 209 several different ways to calculate the probability of a replacement event τ_{ij}
 210 where a copy of the individual on v_i replaces the individual on v_j . In particular,
 211 we can broadly classify these in terms of the order in which v_i and v_j are
 212 picked. For birth-death dynamics (BD) the birth event happens first where
 213 the individual on v_i is chosen for birth with probability b_i . The individual on
 214 v_j is then chosen for death conditional on the individual on v_i giving birth
 215 with probability d_{ij} , thus we have the replacement probability $\tau_{ij} = b_i d_{ij}$. For
 216 death-birth dynamics (DB) the death event happens first where the individual
 217 on v_j is chosen for death with probability d_i . The individual on v_i is then
 218 chosen for birth conditional on the death of individual on v_j with probability
 219 b_{ij} , thus $\tau_{ij} = d_i b_{ij}$. For link dynamics (L) both birth and death events happen
 220 simultaneously and therefore τ_{ij} cannot be decomposed.

221 For each of these dynamics, natural selection can influence the birth (‘B’ ap-
 222 pended to name) or death (‘D’ appended to name) event. We use the definitions
 223 of [28] who extensively studied a set of each of these dynamics. In terms of the
 224 exact formulae of the transition probabilities, we use those of [40] as summarised
 225 in Table 2. In these definitions, the dynamics are a function of the replacement
 226 structure \mathbf{W} and the fitnesses of the individuals such that the individual on
 227 vertex v_n has fitness F_n .

228 3.2. Evolutionary dynamics in our framework

229 In [8] a birth-death dynamics was defined to be used with the territorial
 230 raider model. In this section we shall develop a consistent set of dynamics
 231 for our framework. In particular, we will show that we can adapt the above
 232 dynamics widely used in evolutionary graph theory.

233 To consider the evolution of the population it is useful to think of the in-
 234 dividuals in the population in an abstract way. In particular, individuals in
 235 the population change through time and, therefore, it is better to think of I_i
 236 as a position that an individual can occupy. These positions are referred to
 237 as I -vertices in [8] and have a particular relationship to the places, although
 238 as the population evolves the actual individual, and in particular the type of
 239 individual, occupying the position may change. We will generally simply refer
 240 to these I -vertices as “individuals” but make the distinction where necessary.

241 This leads to a natural way to create evolutionary dynamics for our frame-
 242 work; namely, by mapping each individual I_i to vertex v_i , we can incorporate
 243 the replacement weights of different interaction methods straight into the for-
 244 mulae from Table 2. All that remains is to choose the replacement weights
 245 appropriately.

246 The replacement weights used here are based on the assumption that an
 247 offspring of individual I_i is likely to replace another individual I_j proportional
 248 to the time I_i and I_j spend together. The offspring of I_i can also replace I_i
 249 itself and it does this proportional to the time I_i spends alone. Therefore, when
 250 $i \neq j$, the probability that I_i and I_j meet is given by summing $\chi(m, \mathcal{G})$ over all
 251 m such that $i, j \in \mathcal{G}$. When they meet, we assume that I_i will spend an equal
 252 amount of time with each other individual in group \mathcal{G} and, therefore, weight
 253 $\chi(m, \mathcal{G})$ with $1/(|\mathcal{G}| - 1)$ since there are $|\mathcal{G}| - 1$ other individuals (an alternative
 254 weighting could be $1/|\mathcal{G}|$ that allows interaction within groups larger than one
 255 to contribute to the probability of I_i 's offspring replacing itself). Note that this
 256 is consistent with the payoffs from our public goods game, where each pairwise
 257 payoff equally contributes to the total payoff an individual receives. On the
 258 other hand, when $i = j$, we sum $\chi(m, \mathcal{G})$ over all m such that $\mathcal{G} = \{i\}$. Here
 259 there is no need to weight $\chi(m, \mathcal{G})$ because I_i is alone.

260 The replacement weights are therefore calculated as follows

$$261 \quad w_{ij} = \begin{cases} \sum_m \sum_{i, j \in \mathcal{G}} \frac{\chi(m, \mathcal{G})}{|\mathcal{G}| - 1} & i \neq j, \\ \sum_m \chi(m, \{i\}) & i = j. \end{cases} \quad (3.1)$$

262

263 Thus we have a new set of evolutionary dynamics which can be applied to
 264 our framework in a wide variety of situations (including those that we consider
 265 later in this paper). Note that the dynamics used in [8] is the BDB dynamics
 266 defined from the above process.

267 By our definition \mathbf{W} is symmetric, that is $w_{ij} = w_{ji} \forall i, j$, because the
 268 probability of I_i meeting I_j within any given group is clearly the same as that
 269 of I_j meeting I_i . We also have that \mathbf{W} is doubly stochastic, that is $1 = \sum_j w_{ij} =$
 270 $\sum_i w_{ij}$ for all i, j , because w_{ij} is the proportion of time I_i spends with I_j (with
 271 w_{ii} the proportion of time it spends alone), and it is always in precisely one of
 272 these N categories. In this case, \mathbf{W} is referred to as being *isothermal* [26, 40].

273 We note that the results above hold because of the particular weights w_{ij} that
 274 we have chosen. Although these are natural, they are not the only possibility.
 275 In particular we could have alternative weights where w_{ij} and w_{ji} are not in
 276 general equal and/or where \mathbf{W} is not isothermal.

277 4. Fixation probability and the temperature

278 4.1. The fixation probability

279 The (mean) *fixation probability* ρ^C (ρ^D) is the probability that the offspring
 280 of a randomly placed mutant cooperator (defector) eventually replaces the entire
 281 population. This can be uniformly at random as in [26]; alternatively, one can
 282 use the *mutant appearance distribution* as described in [2]. [8] used a version of
 283 this where they weighted the fixation probabilities using the mean temperature.
 284 For this current work we use the arithmetic mean, as the difference between

285 these two approaches is negligible here, with the arithmetic mean being greater
 286 than or equal to the weighted mean [2]. For more details on how the fixation
 287 probability is calculated, see the Appendix.

288 As in [50], we will use the neutral fixation probability $1/N$ as a benchmark
 289 when comparing cooperators and defectors using their fixation probabilities. In
 290 particular, [50] say that *selection opposes D replacing C* when $\rho_C < 1/N$ and
 291 *selection favours C replacing D* when $1/N < \rho_C$. It is said that type *C* evolves
 292 if both these conditions hold, i.e. if

$$293 \rho_D < 1/N < \rho_C. \quad (4.1)$$

295 4.2. Concepts of temperature

296 In [26] the *in temperature* (or just the *temperature*) of a vertex of an evo-
 297 lutionary graph was introduced to measure how likely an individual occupying
 298 a particular vertex is to be replaced by another individual's offspring. [28]
 299 extended this definition and introduced the *out temperature* of a vertex of an
 300 evolutionary graph to measure how likely the offspring of the individual occupy-
 301 ing that vertex will replace another individual. These definitions of the in and
 302 out temperatures of individual I_n for an evolutionary graph \mathbf{W} are respectively
 303 defined as follows

$$304 T_n^- = \sum_i w_{in} \quad \text{and} \quad T_n^+ = \sum_i w_{ni}. \quad (4.2)$$

306 In general, the in and out temperatures can be different. However, in our
 307 case, \mathbf{W} is doubly stochastic and symmetric and, therefore, the in and out
 308 temperatures are identical. We therefore work with the definition of only in
 309 temperature and simply refer to it as the temperature.

310 An alternative version of the definition of temperature (used in [8]) is the
 311 *strict* temperature that measures how often an individual is likely to be replaced
 312 by other individuals excluding itself. Since \mathbf{W} is doubly stochastic, the strict
 313 temperature of individual I_n for an evolutionary graph \mathbf{W} is given by

$$314 T_n = \sum_{i \neq n} w_{in} = 1 - w_{nn}. \quad (4.3)$$

316 The definition of strict temperature can be extended to subpopulations to
 317 give the strict subpopulation temperature. This measures how likely an in-
 318 dividual in subpopulation \mathcal{Q}_m is to be replaced by an individual in another
 319 subpopulation. Clearly all individuals in a subpopulation have the same tem-
 320 perature (for any of our temperature definitions), since they all have the same
 321 movement distribution. The strict subpopulation temperature is calculated by
 322 summing all weights w_{ij} such that I_i is not part of subpopulation \mathcal{Q}_m and I_j is
 323 part of subpopulation \mathcal{Q}_m giving

$$324 T_{\mathcal{Q}_m} = \sum_{i \in \mathcal{N} \setminus \mathcal{Q}_m} \sum_{j \in \mathcal{Q}_m} w_{ij}. \quad (4.4)$$

Figure 4: Comparing average fixation probability for different complete structures where figure (a) uses DBD dynamics and figure (b) uses DBB dynamics. Each number indicates a subpopulation of a certain density. For example 60 is a complete structure with 2 subpopulations of size 6 and 0 respectively; 2220 has three subpopulations of size 2 and one of size 0. In each case the public goods game parameters are $r = 30, v = 10$ and movement parameter is $h = 30$. We see that in figure (a) for the DBD dynamics, cooperators perform poorly in all cases. In figure (b), cooperators do better for small groups (greater than one). Increasing the number of empty places is beneficial for defectors.

326 This means that if there is only one subpopulation then its strict subpopulation
 327 temperature is 0 by definition, that is, $T_{Q_m} = 0$ if $Q_m = \mathcal{N}$.

328 We note that a strategy introduced in one subpopulation can spread through-
 329 out the population because \mathbf{W} is strongly connected. This implies that if there
 330 is more than one non-empty subpopulation then the strict subpopulation tem-
 331 perature is non-zero for all non-empty subpopulations, that is, $T_{Q_m} > 0$ if
 332 $|Q_m| > 0$. To measure the connectedness of the subpopulations, that is how
 333 often the different subpopulations interact with one another, we use the mean
 334 strict subpopulation temperature that is defined as follows

$$335 \langle T_{Q_m} \rangle = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{m=1}^M |Q_m| T_{Q_m}. \quad (4.5)$$

336

337 5. Cooperation in generalized territorial raider models

338 In this section we study the effect that different model parameters have
 339 on the evolution of cooperation. For models investigating the evolution of co-
 340 operation using evolutionary graph theory, both the evolution and interaction

Figure 5: Comparing average fixation probability for different δ that is the size (or density) of each subpopulation in a complete graph with 4 subpopulations. The public goods game parameters are set to $r = 30$, $v = 11$, the movement parameters are set to $h = 30$ and dynamics used are DBB. As in Figure 4, cooperators evolve better in small groups (larger than 1), namely groups of size two and three, with a small advantage for groups of size four.

341 of individuals are dictated by a fixed structure, following games with a fixed
 342 number of players (almost always two). In our model the replacement structure
 343 emerges from the interactions between individuals, involving games with a
 344 varying number of players, and therefore give us a different perspective on the
 345 evolution of cooperation.

346 We note that no simulations were run to calculate the fixation probabilities
 347 in this paper, rather, all the states of the population were explicitly calculated
 348 following the procedure described in the Appendix.

349 5.1. The effect of the dynamics

350 As we mentioned in Section 1, for evolutionary graph theory models, coop-
 351 eration is favoured when using DBB or BDD dynamics, but not DBD or BDB
 352 dynamics, if the structure allows a cluster of cooperators to form (also see [36]).
 353 This is consistent with [8] where we studied the effect of the BDB dynamics
 354 on the public goods game and cooperators generally performed poorly. It was
 355 shown that defectors dominate regardless of the structure of the population and
 356 the game parameters. We are now in a position to revisit the public goods
 357 game with more flexibility both in terms of the dynamics and the structure of
 358 the population. In terms of the dynamics, the results for BDB and DBD are
 359 identical (as are those for BDD and DBB), because the replacement structure
 360 \mathbf{W} is symmetric and doubly stochastic, so whether birth or death occurs first
 361 (but not whether selection occurs in the first or second position) is irrelevant,
 362 see Table 2. Furthermore, the LB and LD dynamics are equivalent to the BDB
 363 and DBD dynamics, respectively, because \mathbf{W} is isothermal. This can be shown
 364 for LB dynamics (and similarly for LD dynamics) as follows

$$365 \mathfrak{t}_{ij}^{\text{LB}} = \frac{F_i w_{ij}}{\sum_{n,k} F_n w_{nk}} = \frac{F_i w_{ij}}{\sum_n F_n (\sum_k w_{nk})} = \frac{F_i}{\sum_n F_n} w_{ij} = \mathfrak{t}_{ij}^{\text{BDB}}.$$

366

367 Thus in what follows, we only mention one dynamics from each pair, in each
368 case the DB dynamics.

369 For DBD dynamics, the defectors do better than cooperators regardless of
370 the population structure. However, for DBB dynamics, cooperators are favoured
371 over defectors for certain population structures. In particular, these structures
372 that favour cooperators contain small subpopulations, ideally of two individuals.
373 We can see this in Figure 4, where the fixation probability is plotted against
374 different complete population structures for the DBD (Figure 4a) and DBB
375 (Figure 4b) dynamics (as explained in the caption, for each population, each
376 number in its representation corresponds to a subpopulation of that size). For
377 example, for the complete structure 222 where there are 3 subpopulations of
378 size 2, the cooperators outperform defectors by a large amount.

379 To understand why this is the case, consider a population of two individuals
380 where one individual is a cooperator and the other a defector. Within such a
381 population, the cooperator will be less fit than the defector. For DBD dynamics,
382 the least fit individual is most likely to be chosen for death and the fixation
383 probability is proportional to the fitness of the individual. This means that
384 a cooperator has a low fixation probability compared to a defector. However,
385 when using DBB dynamics, one of the two individuals is randomly chosen for
386 death and immediately replaced by the offspring of the other individual. This
387 means that regardless of the fitness of the individual, each type will fixate with
388 probability $1/2$. For sufficiently high home fidelity parameter h , individuals
389 primarily interact with their members of their own subpopulation. Therefore,
390 in such a population where there exists a subpopulation of two individuals, a
391 cluster of two cooperators is more likely to form when using DBB dynamics.
392 This cluster of cooperators has a fitness larger than that of a cluster of defectors,
393 provided that $v > 1$, thereby establishing a stronghold against defectors. In fact,
394 a subpopulation of sufficiently small size (but greater than one) can establish a
395 stronghold against defectors as shown in Figure 5. Here the fixation probability
396 is plotted against a complete structure with four subpopulations that each have
397 size ranging from 1 to 6. Subpopulations of size two are best for cooperation,
398 with their advantage over defectors declining as the size of the subpopulation
399 increases. Given the parameters used, subpopulations of two to four cooperators
400 can successfully resist invasion, but larger subpopulations cannot.

401 5.2. *The effect of the temperature*

402 In [8] the strict temperature and mean group size were both shown to be
403 strongly correlated with the fixation probability, with the effect of the former
404 shown to be stronger. We therefore focus on the temperature, namely the strict
405 subpopulation temperature. Note that in [8] there is one-to-one correspondence
406 between individuals and places, which implies that the strict temperature and
407 strict subpopulation temperature are identical, but this is not the case here.

408 The individual temperature is a measure of how often an individual interacts
409 with other individuals including those who are part of the same subpopulation;
410 thus an individual may have a high temperature but that does not mean it is
411 interacting with individuals from other subpopulations. In particular whenever

Figure 6: Figure (a) plots the mean subpopulation temperature against the home fidelity h for a complete population structure with 3 subpopulations of size 2 each. Figure (b) then plots the fixation probabilities against these values of the mean subpopulation temperature where $r = 30$ and $v = 10$ for the public goods game, and the dynamics used are DBB. In particular, we notice that the fixation probability of the cooperators is decreasing with the mean subpopulation temperature.

Figure 7: Comparing different population structures for the public goods game with various complete graphs for a population size of 12 where (1,12) means there is 1 subpopulation with 12 individuals, (2,6) means there are 2 subpopulations with 6 individuals and so on. We have set $r = 30$ and $v = 10$, home fidelity $h = 30$ and the dynamics used is DBB.

412 individuals are not alone very often, this temperature does not vary so much
413 between different individuals, and so is not a useful concept when there are non-
414 trivial subgroups. The strict subpopulation temperature, on the other hand,
415 considers interactions with individuals only from other subpopulations, and thus
416 can be very variable. We shall see that this temperature is a good predictor of
417 important population properties.

418 The mean strict subpopulation temperature decreases when home fidelity
419 increases as shown in Figure 6a. This is because the individuals are more likely
420 to remain on their home place than visit another place as home fidelity increases,
421 therefore reducing interactions with other subpopulations, and in particular the
422 probability that a member of one subpopulation replaces a member of another
423 at any given time.

424 In [8] it was shown that for BDB dynamics for structures where each sub-
425 population is of size one, there was a linear relationship between the strict
426 (subpopulation) temperature and the fixation probability, with the higher the
427 temperature, the stronger the effect of selection. We investigated this for DBB
428 dynamics, and found an opposite linear effect, which is consistent with [28] who
429 showed that the DBB dynamics suppresses the effect of selection the most for
430 the complete graph. We note that this relationship only holds for relatively
431 weak selection, and we can reverse the relationship (and make it non-linear) by
432 increasing the value of the reward.

433 To promote cooperation we need a structure involving a subpopulation of
434 size at least two. However, whether these structures promote cooperation or
435 not also depends upon the base fitness and reward, and so we assume that the
436 base fitness and reward are sufficiently large for this to be the case, see Section
437 5.4. In this case, decreasing the temperature by increasing the home fidelity
438 promotes cooperation. In particular, the relationship between the mean fixa-
439 tion probability of cooperators and the mean strict subpopulation temperature
440 is negative and nonlinear as shown in Figure 6b. The nonlinearity arises not
441 only from the nonlinear payoff function of the public good game, but also from
442 the fact that there exists a subpopulation that has size at least two. For co-
443 operators, the mean fixation probability is negatively correlated with the mean
444 strict subpopulation temperature because the mean strict subpopulation tem-
445 perature is highest when home fidelity is lowest, i.e. when cooperators cannot
446 separate themselves from the population and form clusters, consequently defec-
447 tion evolves. On the other hand, for low mean strict subpopulation temperature,
448 and so high home fidelity, it is easier to form clusters of cooperators that allows
449 cooperation to evolve. This kind of behaviour is also evident in Figures 4 and
450 7.

451 *5.3. The effect of the number of places*

452 In [8] each individual had their home place and there were no empty places
453 (non home places) that individuals could visit. In our case, individuals can
454 visit non home places and we therefore investigate what effect this has on the
455 evolution of cooperation.

Figure 8: Figure (a) shows the effect of compensating for empty places by increasing the home fidelity such that the probability of staying in their home place, p_{nn} , remains the same. We start at $h = 30$ for the 33 and 222 structures. As an empty place is added, h is increased so that $p_{nn} = 30/31$ for the 330, \dots , 330000 structures and $p_{nn} = 30/32$ for 2220, \dots , 222000 structures. In all cases $r = 30$ and $v = 10$. We can see that after compensating for the above effect, the influence of introducing empty places is both reversed and weakened. Figure (b) shows the mean strict subpopulation temperature dropping off when we compensate for the empty places by increasing the home fidelity such that p_{nn} remains the same.

456 As seen in Figure 4, increasing the number of empty places that subpopu-
 457 lations can visit, whilst keeping all other parameters constant, makes it more
 458 difficult for cooperation to evolve. In particular, this effect is prominent for
 459 structures where cooperators were initially doing well. For example, for the
 460 structure 222 where the cooperators do best, increasing the number of places
 461 significantly reduces their fixation probability whilst increasing that of the de-
 462 fectors. Here increasing the number of places acts in the same way as decreasing
 463 the home fidelity, i.e. as decreasing the amount of time an individual spends in
 464 its home place with members of its subpopulation. Thus the amount of time
 465 an individual spends alone or with individuals not from its subpopulation in-
 466 creases, so that the overall fitness of a cooperative subpopulation will decrease
 467 (they still pay a cost but do not receive a benefit when alone). In terms of
 468 the dynamics, spending more time alone would increase the effect of selection
 469 in DBB dynamics because an individual with higher fitness that is randomly
 470 chosen for death is more likely to be replaced by its own offspring, which affects
 471 the cooperators adversely. A cooperative subpopulation will also have lower
 472 fitness because its members are more likely to interact with individuals from
 473 other subpopulations, therefore exposing them to defectors. The increased in-
 474 teraction between individuals will also increase the effect of selection in DBB
 475 dynamics because an individual with higher fitness that is randomly chosen for
 476 death is less likely to be replaced by an individual with lower fitness in the same
 477 subpopulation.

478 The increase in the number of places can be compensated for by increasing
 479 the home fidelity, so that individuals stay in their home place with the same
 480 probability. This has the effect of decreasing the mean strict subpopulation
 481 temperature as individuals are more likely to spend time with members of their
 482 subpopulation. This is shown in Figure 8, where we can see that the effect of
 483 adding empty places is now reversed, although the strength of this reverse effect
 484 is weak.

485 5.4. The effect of a large home fidelity

486 Consider a well-mixed population of M subpopulations each containing L
 487 individuals, so that $N = ML$, as described in Section 2.1, where h is very
 488 large. Consequently from equation (3.1), $\chi(m, \mathcal{G})$ is approximately 1 if $\mathcal{G} = \mathcal{Q}_m$,
 489 and is approximately 0 otherwise. Thus the fitness of an individual can be
 490 evaluated assuming that we have a group containing precisely all individuals
 491 from its subpopulation with probability 1. Due to the symmetric nature of our
 492 population, the weights for any two individuals in the same subpopulation will
 493 be the same, as will the weights for any two members of different subpopulations.
 494 Denoting the latter as w_O , which will be small, we have $w_{ij} = w_O$ when I_i and
 495 I_j are not in the same subpopulation, and $w_{ij} = w_I \approx [1 - (M-1)Lw_O]/(L-1)$
 496 otherwise, with the probability of self-replacement negligible.

497 It follows that only replacements within subpopulations will happen, except
 498 very rarely. Thus we can assume that the battle within any mixed subpopulation
 499 of cooperator (C) and defector (D) individuals will be resolved with fixation of
 500 one type or the other before any new mixed subpopulation appears.

501 We thus consider a two stage process. Firstly, a new mixed group appears.
 502 This occurs rarely, through the invasion of a cooperator into a defector subpopu-
 503 lation, or a defector into a cooperator subpopulation. Assuming that there are
 504 currently $M_C(M_D = M - M_C)$ cooperator (defector) subpopulations, such a
 505 transition happens with probability

$$506 \quad p_{CI} = \frac{M_D}{M} \frac{M_C L w_O F_L(C)}{(L-1)w_I F_L(D) + O(w_O)} \quad (5.1)$$

507 of a cooperator into a defector subpopulation, or

$$508 \quad p_{DI} = \frac{M_C}{M} \frac{M_D L w_O F_L(D)}{(L-1)w_I F_L(C) + O(w_O)} \quad (5.2)$$

509 of a defector into a cooperator subpopulation. The terms $F_L(C)$ and $F_L(D)$ are
 510 the fitnesses of cooperator and defector individuals within their own subpopu-
 511 lations, and are obtained directly from equations (2.4) and (2.6), and the terms
 512 $O(w_O)$ are of the order of w_O , and very small. Further denoting $x = v/[r(L-1)]$
 513 we obtain that the ratio of the two expressions in equations (5.1) and (5.2), and
 514 thus the relative frequency that the new invasions happen, is thus

$$515 \quad \frac{p_{CI}}{p_{DI}} \approx \left(\frac{F_L(C)}{F_L(D)} \right)^2 = \left(1 + \frac{v-1}{r} \right)^2 \approx (1 + (L-1)x)^2 \quad (5.3)$$

516 for large v and r .

517 The second process considers fixation within a well-mixed group of size L .
 518 Following [23] we obtain the formula

$$519 \quad x_i = \frac{1 + \sum_{j=1}^{i-1} \prod_{k=1}^j \frac{\delta_k}{\beta_k}}{1 + \sum_{j=1}^{L-1} \prod_{k=1}^j \frac{\delta_k}{\beta_k}}, \quad (5.4)$$

520 for the fixation probability of i cooperators within a population of size L . Here
 521 β_k (δ_k) is the probability that the next event is the replacement of a defector
 522 (cooperator) by a cooperator (defector), when the number of cooperators is k .
 523 We have here

$$524 \quad \delta_k = \frac{k(L-k)}{L} \frac{r + \frac{kv}{L-1}}{(L-1)r + ((L-k)k + (k-1)^2) \frac{v}{L-1} - (k-1)}, \quad (5.5)$$

$$525 \quad \beta_k = \frac{k(L-k)}{L} \frac{r + \frac{(k-1)v}{L-1} - 1}{(L-1)r + ((L-k-1)k + k(k-1)) \frac{v}{L-1} - k}. \quad (5.6)$$

527 For sufficiently large r , we obtain

$$528 \quad \frac{\delta_k}{\beta_k} \approx \frac{1+kx}{1+(k-1)x} f_k(x), \quad (5.7)$$

529 where

$$530 \quad f_k(x) = \frac{L-1+(L-2)kx}{L-1+((L-2)k+1)x} < 1. \quad (5.8)$$

531 The fixation probability of a single cooperator in a group of defectors is given
 532 by $\rho_{C,L} = x_1$, and the fixation probability of a single defector in a group of
 533 cooperators is $\rho_{D,L} = 1 - x_{L-1}$. We thus have

$$534 \quad \frac{\rho_{D,L}}{\rho_{C,L}} = \prod_{k=1}^{L-1} \frac{\delta_k}{\beta_k} = \prod_{k=1}^{L-1} \frac{1+kx}{1+(k-1)x} f_k(x) = (1+(L-1)x) \prod_{k=1}^{L-1} f_k(x). \quad (5.9)$$

536 This implies that

$$537 \quad \frac{p_{CI}}{p_{DI}} > \frac{\rho_{D,L}}{\rho_{C,L}}. \quad (5.10)$$

538 Following our assumptions, the population evolves following a succession of
 539 invasions of subpopulations either of cooperators by defectors or of defectors by
 540 cooperators. The probability that the next such event will be the invasion of a
 541 subpopulation of defectors by a cooperator is simply

$$542 \quad \frac{p_{CI} \rho_{C,L}}{p_{CI} \rho_{C,L} + p_{DI} \rho_{D,L}} = \frac{r_S}{1+r_S}, \quad (5.11)$$

543 where $r_S = p_{CI} \rho_{C,L} / p_{DI} \rho_{D,L}$ is the *forward bias* [40] of cooperative groups
 544 within our population. For a cooperator to fixate in the population it must first

545 fixate within its group with probability $\rho_{C,L}$, after which, there is a competition
 546 between groups proceeding precisely as in a Moran process, so that we have

$$547 \quad \rho_C = \rho_{C,L} \frac{1 - 1/r_S}{1 - (1/r_S)^M}, \quad (5.12)$$

548 with the equivalent expression for ρ_D ,

$$549 \quad \rho_D = \rho_{D,L} \frac{r_S - 1}{r_S^M - 1}. \quad (5.13)$$

550 It is clear from equation (5.10) that $r_S > 1$, so that ρ_C is greater than $\rho_{C,L}(1 -$
 551 $1/r_S)$ for any M . Letting M become large means that $1/N = 1/ML$ will be less
 552 than ρ_C , but larger than ρ_D , so that inequality (4.1) holds. This means that
 553 for sufficiently large h, r and v , we have that cooperation evolves for any given
 554 subpopulation size L . Thus cooperation can potentially evolve for arbitrarily
 555 large subpopulations, although as we have seen previously, it is easier for smaller
 556 subpopulations.

557 6. Discussion

558 In [10] a new framework for the flexible modelling of structured populations
 559 using multiplayer interactions was introduced, see also [8, 13, 11]. This work
 560 built on classical evolutionary graph theory, but was limited in terms of the
 561 dynamics used. In this paper we have developed this framework further. Most
 562 importantly we have developed a full range of dynamics to apply in the frame-
 563 work, which will allow us to consider many different evolutionary scenarios. In
 564 particular these can be applied for the fully independent model in general, not
 565 just the examples considered here, enabling us to use a fuller range of the pos-
 566 sibilities that our flexible framework allows. Thus this paper can be thought to
 567 complete the basic development phase of our work.

568 We have then developed the fully independent model to incorporate subpop-
 569 ulations and in particular consider a generalized version of the territorial raider
 570 model introduced in [8]. This is beneficial because previously the fully inde-
 571 pendent model, represented in the bipartite graph in Figure 1, would require
 572 a vertex for every individual as well as an additional vertex for every available
 573 place. Now we just need a vertex per subpopulation, potentially allowing a small
 574 number of very large subpopulations to be considered, which would not have
 575 been possible previously. Thus this generalization allows us to look at much
 576 larger populations, which most real populations are, but still be able to use
 577 some analytical methods. The fact that larger populations can be considered
 578 without increasing complexity in turn allows us to incorporate other features
 579 that will enable our model to be applied more widely, as discussed below relating
 580 to mobile populations.

581 This type of structure has been considered in a slightly different context,
 582 for example, the island- or community-structured populations of [53]. In this
 583 model interactions occur at multiple levels, interactions between community

584 members being more common than those with non-community members where
585 interaction occurs at multiple levels. Members of one community first play a
586 public goods game and then join the members of another community and play a
587 public goods game such that, at the highest level, the entire population plays a
588 public goods game. This is in contrast to our case, where individuals only play
589 a game if they are present in the same place at the same time. They showed
590 that cooperation can evolve when DBB dynamics are used and selection is weak
591 within communities, which is consistent with our results.

592 We note that the framework of [8] is capable of modelling far wider be-
593 haviour than that developed here, in particular it is able to consider dynamic
594 populations whose distributions continuously change due to their history, and
595 the interactions that they have. Thus it can incorporate the type of situations
596 with mobile populations modelled in [55, 47]. In particular, movement can
597 follow a stochastic process in which the individuals move depending upon their
598 current state as in [16]. This is an important step in the development of realistic
599 population models, for example related to territorial behaviour where animals
600 can cover long distances, or movement behaviour varies throughout the year as
601 seen in, for example, African wild dogs that live in packs [17]. In a recently
602 submitted paper [39] we have developed a Markov chain version of our model,
603 and again consider a combination of theoretical developments and the specific
604 application of the evolution of cooperation. This is our first step in the type of
605 history-dependent analysis described above.

606 We then applied our new methodology to an example, considering the evolu-
607 tion of cooperation within a population involving subpopulations. We saw as in
608 evolutionary graph theory that the choice of dynamics is crucial, and that DBD
609 (and BDB) dynamics would not allow cooperation to evolve, but that DBB (and
610 BDD) would, which is consistent with [36]. Further, using the latter dynamics,
611 the size and the level of isolation of the subpopulations is important, with the
612 smaller the subpopulations and the greater the isolation, the greater the chance
613 for cooperation to evolve. Unsurprisingly, the larger the level of reward v , the
614 better the cooperators do. In particular, the larger the subpopulations, the
615 larger the reward v required for cooperation to evolve; note that this is similar
616 to the requirement that the benefit-to-cost ratio exceeds the average number of
617 neighbours an individual has from [36].

618 We see from Figure 6 that our new idea of strict subgroup temperature
619 is important in explaining the level of cooperation that evolves. Low (high)
620 temperature helps promote the invasion of cooperators (defectors). In particu-
621 lar, higher temperatures allow cooperators to cluster more strongly and benefit
622 more from cooperating with one another. We note that this raises a more gen-
623 eral question about temperature. Within subpopulation temperature includes
624 replacement weights between pairs of individuals from different subpopulations,
625 but excludes weights between pairs from within the same subpopulation. What
626 if two individuals have very similar, but not identical, movement distributions
627 (and thus whilst formally not within the same subpopulation, for practical pur-
628 poses they might as well be)? Under the current definition no distinction is made
629 between this and two individuals whose distributions are completely different.

630 We will investigate this question in later work.

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783 Appendix A.

784 A state of the population gives the type of each individual in the population.
 785 Let \mathcal{S} be a state of the population such that $n \in \mathcal{S}$ if and only if I_n is a
 786 cooperator. There are then 2^N different states of which $\mathcal{N}(\emptyset)$ is the state in
 787 which there are all cooperators (defectors). Using any dynamics, the probability
 788 of transitioning from state \mathcal{S} to \mathcal{S}' is defined as follows

$$789 P_{\mathcal{S}\mathcal{S}'} = \sum_{i \in \mathcal{S}} \tau_{ij} \text{ for } \mathcal{S}' = \mathcal{S} \cup \{j\}, \text{ or } \sum_{i \notin \mathcal{S}} \tau_{ij} \text{ for } \mathcal{S}' = \mathcal{S} \setminus \{j\}, \text{ or } \sum_{\substack{i,j \in \mathcal{S} \\ i,j \notin \mathcal{S}}} \tau_{ij} \text{ for } \mathcal{S}' = \mathcal{S},$$

790 (A.1)

791 or 0 otherwise.

792 Cooperators (defectors) is said to *fixate* from state \mathcal{S} in the population when,
 793 starting from state \mathcal{S} , every defector (cooperator) is replaced by a cooperator
 794 (defector), that is the population reaches state $\mathcal{N}(\emptyset)$. At this point no further
 795 changes are possible, since one type is extinct, and so the population remains
 796 in this state. Let $\rho_{\mathcal{S}}^C$ be the probability that cooperators fixate from any initial
 797 state \mathcal{S} , then this is obtained by solving the following system of equations

$$798 \rho_{\mathcal{S}}^C = \sum_{\mathcal{S}'} P_{\mathcal{S}\mathcal{S}'} \rho_{\mathcal{S}'}^C$$

799 (A.2)

800 with boundary conditions

$$801 \rho_{\emptyset}^C = 0 \quad \text{and} \quad \rho_{\mathcal{N}}^D = 1$$

802 (A.3)

803 where $P_{\mathcal{S}\mathcal{S}'}$ is the probability of transitioning from state \mathcal{S} to \mathcal{S}' . The probability
 804 $\rho_{\mathcal{S}}^D$ that defectors fixate from any initial state \mathcal{S} is obtained in the same way
 805 with the boundary conditions reversed.

806 The mean fixation probability of cooperators (defectors) is a, potentially,
 807 weighted average of the probabilities $\rho_{\mathcal{S}}^C$ ($\rho_{\mathcal{S}}^D$), over \mathcal{S} when there is only one
 808 cooperator (defector) in the population, that is $|\mathcal{S}| = 1$ ($|\mathcal{S}| = N - 1$). There are
 809 two common weightings used; uniformly weighted (as we use here) or weighted
 810 in proportion to the mutant appearance distribution as defined in [2].

811 The evolution of the population is essentially described by an absorbing
 812 Markov chain. The mean fixation probability is therefore calculated by com-
 813 puting the state transition probabilities that are then used to construct the state
 814 transition matrix of the Markov chain. The state transition matrix is then used
 815 to calculate the fixation probability see, for example, [23] for explanation of how
 816 this is done.